

Spray combustion of fast-pyrolysis bio-oils under engine-like conditions

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ABSTRACT

In the EU funded SmartCHP project, biomass derived fast-pyrolysis bio-oil (FPBO) is used to fuel modified stationary diesel engines for combined heat and power applications. In this study, the spray combustion characteristics of fast-pyrolysis bio-oil and FPBO/ethanol blends are experimentally investigated in a combustion research unit. Due to the special physicochemical properties of fast-pyrolysis bio-oil, major modifications are made to the combustion research unit to facilitate testing this fuel, including the installation of a high-temperature chamber and a heavy-fuel oil injection system. Experimental tests are carried out at a chamber wall temperature of 750 °C and an ambient pressure of 50 bar. The pressure-based heat release analysis is used to evaluate fuel ignition and combustion characteristics, while a high-speed imaging technique is adopted to visualize natural luminosity of spray flames through a borescope.

Results show that fast-pyrolysis bio-oil has lower sooting tendency than diesel, and it significantly alleviates the fuel dribble phenomenon. At injection pressure of 300 bar, the poor atomization of fast-pyrolysis bio-oil leads to rather grainy-looking spray flame images, and nozzle orifices becoming clogged within couple of injections. The increase of injection pressure to 900 bar results in an obvious improvement of the atomization quality and nozzle durability for fast-pyrolysis bio-oil. Adding ethanol into fast-pyrolysis bio-oil could improve fuel atomization and further reduce the natural luminosity. The ignition delay of fast-pyrolysis bio-oil is slightly retarded by 10% ethanol addition, while it is advanced by 30% ethanol addition.

Introduction

Replacing fossil-based fuels by sustainable biomass-derived fuels is a key measure to contribute to net-zero carbon dioxide emissions in the future. According to the International Energy Agency net-zero emissions scenario prediction, the total bioenergy demand could increase from 63 EJ in 2020 to around 100 EJ in 2050, where the contribution of liquid biofuels is expected to expand from 3.7 EJ to 15.4 EJ [1]. Fast pyrolysis is an efficient process to convert solid biomass to liquid bio-oils. The organic feedstocks are first heated rapidly to 450–600 °C in the absence of oxygen [2]. After a short residence time of several seconds, the formed vapor is quickly condensed to a liquid product, called fast pyrolysis bio-oil (FPBO) [3]. According to the European Union (EU) “Fit for 55” package, FPBO belongs to the advanced bioliquid class if it is produced from cellulosic and lignocellulosic materials, such as agricultural and forestry residues, wastes, energy crops, or aquatic biomass [4].

The EU funded SmartCHP project is aiming to develop a smart and flexible small-scale combined heat and power (CHP) system running on fast-pyrolysis bio-oil (FPBO) produced from agricultural and forestry

residues [5]. In the SmartCHP system, FPBO is expected to fuel stationary diesel engines for power generation. Several review articles comprehensively detailed the physical and chemical properties of FPBO [6–9] all showing its properties highly depend on the type of feedstock and the production process. FPBO has a high water content (15–30 wt%) and a high oxygen content (30–50 wt%) [10,11]. Hence, different from pyrolysis oil made from waste tires [12,13] and plastic [14,15], FPBO is a polar liquid which is not compatible with diesel fuels. It also contains some organic solids (polymer and char) and ash particles (metal and salts). Compared to commercial diesel fuels, FPBO has a high viscosity and low-chemical reactivity. Other properties of FPBO to consider are its acidity and its tendency to polymerize. The high acidity (pH 2–3) of FPBO may lead to corrosion in metal [16] and elastomeric materials [17] of the fuel supply and injection system. Its tendency to polymerize at elevated temperatures may lead to nozzle clogging and coking, since the large-weight molecules formed from polymerization are prone to become gummy polymers and to precipitate from the liquid phase [18].

The special properties of FPBO limit its direct (drop-in) application in engines. A potential solution is to upgrade FPBO chemically [19], e.g., by catalytic hydrogenation [20]. The upgraded product has similar

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Nomenclature

p_{init}	Initial chamber pressure	EU	European Union
p_{inj}	Injection pressure	FPBO	Fast pyrolysis bio-oil
T_{wall}	Chamber wall temperature	HFO	Heavy-fuel oil
τ_{inj}	Injection duration	HRR	Heat release rate
aSOI	After start of injection	HT	High temperature
CHP	Combined heat and power	LHV	Lower heating value
CMOS	Complementary metal–oxide semiconductor	MFB	Mass fraction burned
CO	Carbon monoxide	NL	Natural luminosity
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide	NO _x	Nitrogen oxides
CRU	Combustion research unit	SOA	Start of actuation
CVCC	Constant-volume combustion chamber	SOI	Start of injection
EOI	End of injection	TDC	Top dead center
		UHC	Unburned hydrocarbon

physicochemical properties as diesel, with which it can therefore be blended without problems [21]. However, the extra chemical treatments would increase the cost as well as the lift-cycle CO₂ emission. Hence, in many contemporary studies, FPBO is blended with a higher-quality base-fuel to fuel diesel engines. Due to its polar properties, it is a common practice to mix FPBO with polar solvents such as ethanol or butanol. However, both FPBO and low-carbon alcohols have low chemical reactivity, so that extra measures are taken by researchers to burn FPBO blends in diesel engines, including: 1) improving fuel ignitability by adding ignition improvers, and 2) raising in-cylinder temperature at engine top dead center (TDC) by pilot diesel injections, intake air preheating, or elevated compression ratios. Lee et al. blended 20–40 wt% FPBO into ethanol and achieved testing this FPBO/ethanol blend in a dual-injection diesel engine with a pilot diesel injection [22,23]. Results showed that stable engine operation was possible with such a dual-injection strategy, while the fuel conversion efficiency was slightly decreased compared to pure diesel combustion. Using FPBO/ethanol blends significantly reduced nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and soot emissions but slightly increased carbon monoxide (CO) and unburned hydrocarbon (UHC) emissions. Kim et al. tested the blends of FPBO (10–30 wt%), n-butanol, and two ignition improvers (polyethylene glycol 400 and 2-ethylhexyl) in a modified diesel engine where they also elevated the compression ratio from 17.1 to 25 [24]. The engine performance and emission results of their FPBO/n-butanol/improver blends were similar to those of FPBO/ethanol blends with pilot diesel injection [22,23]. In our previous work, a combustion research unit was employed to investigate the ignition properties of ternary blends of FPBO (0–30%), n-butanol, and 2-ethylhexyl nitrate [25]. Results showed that ambient temperature had a significant influence on the ignition and combustion processes of FPBO blends, and that two-stage ignition was observed for all cases in the chamber wall temperature range of 505–580 °C. Higher FPBO content showed little effect on the low-temperature reaction phase, while it delayed the peak of heat release rate in the high-temperature reaction phase.

By major engine modification, a few studies achieved high FPBO proportion or even pure FPBO operation in diesel engines for power generation. For instance, van de Beld et al. reported on the use of pure FPBO in a modified 1-cylinder diesel engine. They manufactured an in-house fuel pump and injector with corrosion resistant materials, increased the engine compression ratio from 17.6 to 22.4, and employed intake air preheating up to 200 °C. Moreover, fuel preheating was also adopted to increase the fluidity of FPBO [26]. In a following publication, a continuous and stable run of 52 h was achieved in this 1-cylinder engine [27]. Subsequently, they modified a modern 4-cylinder 48 kW diesel engine to enable fueling with pure FPBO for further research.

The above experimental trials present a promising prospect to use FPBO as an alternative fuel in diesel engines for combined power and heat generation. However, there is still a lack of fundamental

investigation of FPBO spray combustion characteristics under engine-like conditions. In this study, a modified combustion research unit (CRU) is used to provide similar thermodynamic boundary conditions as an engine at TDC. Furthermore, the spray combustion characteristics of FPBO and FPBO blends are studied using high-speed natural luminosity visualization via the optically accessible bottom adaptor of the CRU. The present work is structured as follows: a method section introduces the CRU setup, high-speed diagnostics, and tested conditions. Next, the experimental results are analyzed and discussed. Finally, the general conclusions are given.

Methods

Combustion research unit

The combustion research unit (CRU) from Fueltech Solutions AS is employed to study the combustion processes of FPBO and its blends under engine-like conditions. Within a so-called constant-volume combustion chamber (CVCC), the CRU provides the high-temperature, high-pressure ambient conditions for autoignition and combustion of the injected fuel sprays. Previous studies [25,28] have detailed the basic working principle of the CRU, including the gas intake/exhaust procedure, temperature control, and standard fuel injection systems. However, similar to the engine experiments mentioned above, repeatable testing of FPBO in the original CRU is impossible due to its special physicochemical properties. Therefore, in this study, major modifications are made to the CRU to facilitate testing FPBO.

Firstly, the standard chamber is replaced to realize a higher ambient temperature for FPBO autoignition. The left panel of Fig. 1 shows the dimensions of the new chamber. This high-temperature (HT) chamber is smaller than the standard one but capable of providing chamber wall temperatures (T_{wall}) up to 750 °C. Table 1 compares CRU operation parameters before and after the modifications. In the standard chamber, there are two thermocouples installed inside the different height of the chamber side walls to measure the chamber wall temperatures. Correspondingly, according to the temperature readings, the CRU controls the heating power of the two electric heaters to limit the vertical non-uniformity of wall temperature within 1 °C. However, due to the smaller dimensions, there is only one electric heater in the high-temperature chamber. Hence, the temperature reading from the upper thermocouple is used as chamber wall temperature. During the experiments, the temperature difference measured by two thermocouples is below 10 °C.

Secondly, the standard diesel fuel injection system is upgraded to a heavy-fuel oil (HFO) injection system to adapt for high-viscosity fuels like FPBO. As shown in the right panel of Fig. 1, a separate HFO circuit is established in this injection system [29]. The working medium in the conventional control circuit, diesel, is pressurized in the pressure

Fig. 1. Schematic overview of the CRU combustion chamber equipped with a borescope (left) and the heavy-fuel oil injection system (right).

Table 1

CRU operation parameters before and after modifications (with HT chamber and HFO injection system).

Parameter	Before modification ^(a)	After modification
Chamber volume [mL]	475	300
Chamber wall temperature, T_{wall} [°C]	300–590	300–750
Initial chamber pressure, p_{init} [bar]	20–70	20–70
Injection pressure, p_{inj} [bar]	300–1600	300–1000
Injection duration, τ_{inj} [μ s]	0–1500	0–1000

(a) CRU operation parameters before modification are based on Ref. [25].

amplifier to up to 1000 bar. Then, part of the pressurized diesel is supplied to the accumulator, which maintains a high pressure in the upper part of the injector plunger to ensure that the nozzle valve is properly closed between injection cycles. In the HFO circuit, the tested fuel sample (in this study, FPBO and FPBO blends) is first pressurized in the fuel pressurizer driven by the high-pressure diesel circuit, and then supplied to the HFO injector. In the HFO injector, both the injector body and the nozzle are manufactured to have a fuel return hole, which is used to conveniently drain and flush the HFO fuel lines. The separation of the tested fuel samples from the more vulnerable pressure amplifier improves the stability and durability of the fuel supply system. The nozzle used in the HFO injector is the same as that in the standard Bosch CRIP2 injector, which has 7 holes with an orifice diameter of 160 μ m and an umbrella angle of 158°. The HFO injection system can provide fuel injection pressures ranging between 300 and 1000 bar.

Heat release analysis

The chamber pressure is recorded by the CRU at a rate of 50 kHz (intervals of 0.02 ms), from the start of injection (SOI) to the following 45 ms. It is noteworthy that the period between start of the actuation (SOA) and start of the injection (SOI), i.e., the injector hydraulic delay, is approximately 0.34 ms for the HFO injector. Following the data processing method shown in Fig. 2, the chamber pressure data output by the CRU is used to calculate the heat release rate (HRR) and mass fraction burned (MFB) profiles. These are then used to characterize the ignition and combustion processes of the tested fuels. The time delay caused by the propagation of pressure waves to the pressure sensor is corrected using the local speed of sound and distance between the spray and the pressure sensor. The heat-transfer rate to the chamber wall is also compensated for in the HRR calculation by using a basic heat conduction model. A more detailed explanation of the CRU heat release analysis can be found in Ref. [25].

High-speed visualization of natural luminosity

A high-speed CMOS camera (Photron Fastcam SA3) equipped with a borescope (angle of view of 48°) is used to record the broadband natural luminosity (NL) images of spray flames through the small optical window of the CRU bottom adapter. As shown in Fig. 1, the diameter of the region that can be visualized is smaller than the chamber diameter (85 mm), meaning that the direct flame/wall impingement cannot be observed using this setup.

In CRU experiments, the energizing time of the injector solenoid is limited by 1 ms, meaning that a high time resolution is desired for flame

Fig. 2. Determination of heat release rate (HRR) and mass fraction burned (MFB) according to CRU chamber pressure data.

visualization. In this study, a frame rate of 2 kfps with an image resolution of 640×688 pixels is adopted to record all 7 plumes of the fuel spray flames. For better time resolution, a frame rate of 10,000 fps with image resolution of 512×144 pixels is used to record a single plume. To avoid overexposure or low signal-to-noise levels, the exposure time of the camera is adjusted to adapt to the NL intensity under different tested cases. For example, the higher sooting tendency of diesel generally leads to a higher natural luminosity, so that a shorter exposure time (indicated as “shutter” in some images) of $25 \mu\text{s}$ is adopted when recording diesel spray flames.

Tested fuels and conditions

The purpose of the experiments carried out in this study is to investigate the fundamental spray combustion characteristics of pure FPBO and FPBO blended with a small amount of ethanol (10–30 wt%). Table 2 compares the properties of diesel, FPBO, and ethanol. The wood based FPBO sample is provided by BTG Biomass Technology Group BV. Commercial EN590 diesel is tested as the benchmark fuel. Table 3 lists the remaining CRU test conditions. As mentioned before, experimental tests of FPBO require a higher ambient temperature since it has a low chemical reactivity. In engine application, both elevated compression ratio and intake preheating are generally required for FPBO operation. Hence, in this study, the chamber wall temperature of the CRU is set to the upper limit, $750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, to simulate the in-cylinder temperature at TDC of a modified engine. The initial chamber pressure is fixed at 50 bar for all the test cases. Parametric studies on two injection pressures, 300 and 900 bar, are also implemented. The injection pressure of 300 bar is representative for a mechanical pump-line-nozzle system, while 900 bar approaches the injection pressure of a common-rail injection system. Unless otherwise specified, 5 injections are recorded at each test condition to obtain ensemble averaged results. Previous research performed on the same setup verified that statistically relevant results can be derived from 5 injections because of the well-controlled thermal conditions provided by the CRU [25]. The time interval between two injections in the CRU is around 2 min to ensure stable operating conditions.

Results and discussion

This section presents the results of the heat release analysis and high-speed NL images for pure FPBO and FPBO/ethanol blends. First, the results of pure FPBO at low and high injection pressures are presented, respectively. Subsequently, the effects of ethanol addition on FPBO spray combustion are discussed.

Pure FPBO combustion at low injection pressure

Pure FPBO is first tested at an injection pressure of 300 bar. Previous studies reported that FPBO tends to quickly block the injector nozzles in

Table 2
Fuel properties of diesel, FPBO, and ethanol.

Property	Unit	Diesel	FPBO ^(a)	Ethanol
LHV	MJ/kg	42.6	16.4	28.9
	MJ/L	34.9	19.2	22.5
Density	kg/L	0.82	1.17	0.78
C	wt.%	85.0	42.8	52.2
H	wt.%	12.6	7.8	13.0
O	wt.%	–	49.2	34.8
Water	wt.%	–	24.1	–
Solid	wt.%	–	0.04	–
Viscosity (40 °C)	cSt	2.7	21	1.1
pH	–	–	2.6	–
Cetane number	–	54.8	–	8

(a) Properties of FPBO are based on Ref. [27].

Table 3
Tested conditions in the CRU.

Parameter	Value
Chamber wall temperature, T_{wall} [$^\circ\text{C}$]	750
Initial chamber pressure, p_{init} [bar]	50
Injection pressure, p_{inj} [bar]	300, 900
Injection duration, τ_{inj} [μs]	1000

engine experiments [8,30]. Hence, the continuous 20 injections of FPBO are performed using the same nozzle. Fig. 3 shows the heat release analysis results of five out of a total of 20 injections (injections numbered 4, 7, 13, 16, and 20) of FPBO. The ensemble averaged results of diesel at the same test condition (using a new nozzle) are also presented in dash-dotted lines. From the HRR profiles of FPBO, it becomes clear that the peak value reduces with the number of injections, while the phasing is slightly delayed. As illustrated by the accompanied natural luminosity images in Fig. 4, this is caused by severe nozzle clogging that happens within several injections. As shown in the magnified image in Fig. 4, during the 13th injection, 3 out of 7 orifices are fully blocked and one orifice is partially blocked. One of the remaining spray plumes is deflected from the spray axis of that nozzle. In the 16th injection, the effective number of orifices is further reduced to only two. The influence of nozzle blocking on the effective injected volume can be quantitatively evaluated from the MFB profiles. The nominal injected volume at each test case is a constant (which is determined by testing diesel at the same conditions [25]). Therefore, the effective injection volume scales directly to the maximum MFB if all the injected fuel is assumed to be fully combusted (which is reasonable at $T_{\text{wall}} = 750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $p_{\text{init}} = 50$

Fig. 3. Heat release rate and mass fraction burned results for FPBO and diesel at injection pressure of 300 bar.

Fig. 4. Natural luminosity images for FPBO and diesel spray flames at injection pressure of 300 bar. The results are shown using a false color scale. Numbers in the top right corner of the individual panels represent the time after SOI in milliseconds. The panel highlighted by a red box at 2.16 ms aSOI is enlarged on the righthand side of this figure to illustrate the consequences of nozzle clogging. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

bar). For example, the effective injected volume is substantially reduced to only 20% within 20 injections. As mentioned before, the nozzle blocking is caused by the clogging and coking behavior of FPBO, due to its polymerization tendency at elevated temperature as well as its solid/ash content.

FPBO has a significantly reduced chemical reactivity when compared to diesel, leading to a retarded ignition delay and peak HRR phasing (both on the order of 0.5 ms) at injection pressure of 300 bar, as shown in Fig. 3. However, the first several injections of FPBO show comparable peak values of HRR when compared to diesel combustion, although the volumetric lower heating value (LHV) of FPBO is only 19.2 MJ/L, around half of LHV of diesel (34.9 MJ/L). Evidently, the FPBO burns in a more pre-mixed burn fashion, without the additional mixing-limited burn and a so-called burn-out phase with a tail-like shown by the diesel curve beyond approximately 3 to 4 ms after start of injection (aSOI). As shown in Fig. 4, relatively severe fuel dribble is observed for diesel combustion at this injection pressure, which lasts for several milliseconds after the end of injection (EOI). Interestingly, the combustion reactions of FPBO end at around 3 ms aSOI in the HRR panel, without obvious fuel dribble in the NL images. This could be because the fuel remaining in the nozzle sac after the end of injection is less prone to cause fuel dribbling because of the higher viscosity and higher surface tension of FPBO compared with diesel [31].

Different from diesel combustion, there are many bright, distinct parcels observed in the FPBO spray flames at the injection pressure of 300 bar, which is referred to as a “grainy spray flame structure” in this study. The grainy structure indicates that the atomization quality of FPBO at lower injection pressures is poor when compared to diesel. The parcels in these structures need more time to evaporate and to be oxidized after EOI, which could lead to soot formation and UHC

emissions in real engines.

Pure FPBO combustion at high injection pressure

After changing the blocked nozzle, pure FPBO and diesel are then tested at an injection pressure of 900 bar. The typical natural luminosity results from one of single tests are shown in Fig. 5. It is noted that no visible nozzle clogging is observed for 20 injections of FPBO at this injection pressure. FPBO spray flames at high injection pressure are much smoother than those at low injection pressures, without the previously observed grainy spray flame structure. According to Bernoulli’s principle, the nozzle exit velocities are 292 m/s for FPBO injected at 300 bar and 539 m/s at 900 bar, respectively. Considering the increased flow velocity at higher injection pressure may also result in a “smoother” spray flame due to motion blur, the exposure time is reduced from 200 μ s at injection pressure of 300 bar to 50 μ s at 900 bar. Therefore, it is concluded that FPBO atomization is improved considerably at elevated injection pressure, and hence the spray characteristics of FPBO are much more similar to the benchmark diesel cases.

The left-most panels of Fig. 6 shows the ensemble averaged NL images of diesel and FPBO, respectively. The nozzle tip is located at the middle point of the left edge in each panel. As mentioned before, a higher frame rate of 10 kfps is implemented to record one out of 7 plumes. For diesel combustion, the intense flame luminosity illuminates the liquid fuel spray, identifying that the end of injection (EOI) is at around 1.4 ms aSOI. After the end of injection, combustion recession (as described by Knox et al. [32,33]) can be clearly observed for both FPBO and diesel spray flames.

To better understand the difference between diesel and FPBO combustion, the radially integrated NL intensity is calculated and shown as a

Fig. 5. Natural luminosity images for FPBO and diesel spray flames at injection pressure of 900 bar.

Fig. 6. Results of FPBO and diesel at injection pressure of 900 bar focused on a single spray plume to increase the camera frame rate. Left: ensemble averaged NL images. Right: radially integrated NL intensity as a function of axial distance and time. $NL \times 4$ indicates that the NL intensity is enlarged by a factor of four to improve the visualization. The signal in white dashed triangles (left panels) and boxes (right panels) contains the noise caused by the light reflected from chamber top surface. Black arrows denote combustion recession after the EOI, and the red dashed box is caused by fuel dribble after the EOI. Bilinear interpolation is used to enhance image resolution in the integrated intensity panels. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

function of axial distance and time, as shown in the right-most panels of Fig. 6. It is noteworthy that the pixel values in FPBO NL images are first divided by a factor of two, to compensate for the longer shutter time. However, they are then multiplied by a factor of four to improve the visualization (denoted as $NL \times 4$). More details on obtaining radially integrated graphs can be found in Refs. [34,35]. For both fuels, the ignition delays are only marginally shorter than the injection durations, meaning that a great part of the fuel burns in a pre-mixed burn event. The spray flames of both diesel and FPBO do stabilize for a short period before EOI, while the entire flame luminosity-based structure of FPBO moves upstream approximately 6 mm compared to diesel. Even though quantitative measurement of the flame lift-off length relies on OH^* chemiluminescence imaging [35], the current NL results indicate that the oxygen content in FPBO alleviates the oxygen needed from the entrainment of ambient gases, and hence reduces the flame lift-off length. While a shorter lift-off length is generally associated with increased soot emissions [36,37], the NL signal in fact is clearly approximately a factor of 4 lower. It is noted that the NL signal in the white dashed box contains the noise caused by the light reflected from the smooth area in the top surface of the combustion chamber (corresponding to the injector cooling system with a radius of 10 mm, see Fig. 1). The black arrows denote combustion recession after the end of injection. For diesel combustion, the NL signal in the red dashed box is caused by fuel dribble after the end of injection. The initial velocity of fuel dribble is quite low, leading to poor atomization. Hence, the dribbled fuel stays near the nozzle and its visible combustion lasts around 1 ms, which is associated with high hydrocarbon emissions [31].

Fig. 7 shows the HRR, MFB, and cumulative NL results of FPBO and diesel at injection pressure of 900 bar. Heat release analysis results show that the increase of injection pressure not only shortens the ignition delay of both FPBO and diesel, but also reduces the ignition delay differences between these two fuels. Besides, it seems that higher injection pressure could curb fuel dribbling since the combustion duration for the dribbled diesel is significantly shortened.

The cumulative NL results are calculated by adding up all pixel values in each frame and then compensating for the differences in shutter settings. For the NL images of diesel, there are overexposed areas between 0.96 and 2.36 ms aSOI, and hence the dash-dotted line is used in the cumulative NL panel to denote the underestimation of NL in this period. The broadband natural luminosity shot by high-speed camera is generally dominated by soot radiation [38]. In a study by Hessel et al. [39], it is stated that it could be challenging to estimate the actual distribution of soot by viewing the NL images for the following reasons: 1) the NL signal recorded by a camera accumulates the light along a line of

sight, instead of a single point source; 2) soot temperature dominates the radiation intensity while the temperature distribution in a spray flame is non-uniform; and 3) at a certain temperature, the increased soot concentration also increases local image brightness. However, the cumulative NL still provides an overall estimation on sooting tendency of spray flames. While the volumetric LHV of diesel is twice as large as that of FPBO, the cumulative NL of diesel is more than four times higher than that of FPBO. This indicates that FPBO has much lower sooting tendency than diesel, which can be explained by the oxygen content in the fuel [40,41].

FPBO with addition of ethanol

Different amounts of ethanol, 10 wt% and 30 wt%, are added into FPBO and tested in the CRU, referred to as “F + E10” and “F + E30,” respectively. Fig. 8 shows the HRR and cumulative NL results of FPBO/ethanol blends. Based on HRR profiles, small amounts of ethanol addition slightly lower the peak value of the HRR, while it also has a minor influence on the ignition delay. From the magnified HRR plot, it seems that compared with pure FPBO, the ignition delay is retarded by 10% ethanol addition while it is advanced by 30% ethanol addition. Such difference can originate from a change in physical ignition delay (breakup, vaporization, and fuel-ambient mixing), as well as a change in chemical ignition delay (initial formation and chain reaction of free radicals) before the detectable autoignition. It is generally believed that the chemical reactivity of ethanol is lower than that of FPBO, indicating that more ethanol addition results in a longer chemical ignition delay. However, it was reported that ethanol addition could significantly reduce both viscosity and surface tension [27], which improves the atomization and hence shortens the physical ignition delay. Therefore, the behavior of ignition delay with the addition of ethanol could be explained by the above-mentioned effects.

Fig. 9 shows the NL images for FPBO/ethanol blends. The pixel values in FPBO NL images are doubled to compensate for the shorter shutter time. The volumetric LHV of ethanol is slightly larger than that of FPBO, while the addition of ethanol lowers the NL intensity, indicating that the ethanol addition could further inhibit the soot formation in FPBO spray flames. This is an interesting experimental observation since the oxygen content in FPBO is generally higher than that in ethanol (49.2 wt% versus 34.8 wt%, see Table 2). A possible explanation is discussed here. All the oxygen content in ethanol is contained within the functional hydroxyl group, while almost half of the oxygen content in FPBO is contributed by the water content (24.1 wt%). The study from Westbrook et al. [42] showed that the C–O moieties imbedded in

Fig. 7. HRR, MFB, and cumulative NL profiles of FPBO and diesel at the injection pressure of 900 bar. In the bottom panel, the cumulative NL is shown after compensating for the difference in shutter settings; the dash-dotted part of the line in the diesel profile means these data are underestimated since some regions in the NL images are overexposed.

oxygenated fuels survive the fuel-rich ignition and alter the chemical reaction pathway, leading to the reduced soot precursor species during the rich ignition. Compared with the direct contribution to soot reduction of oxygen-containing functional groups, the water content of FPBO seems to contribute in an “indirect” way, e.g., promoting the reverse reaction of elementary water-formation reactions and reducing local flame temperature due to the high specific heat capacity [43]. According to this study, it is likely that the oxygen-containing functional group plays a more important role in inhibiting soot formation compared to the oxygen content coming from the fuel water content. Future quantitative soot measurements, e.g., engine bench experiments with a soot analyzers or CVCC experiments with quantitative soot measurement

Fig. 8. The results of HRR and cumulative NL for FPBO/ethanol blends with ethanol mass fraction of 0%, 10%, and 30%.

Fig. 9. Natural luminosity images for FPBO/ethanol blends with ethanol mass fraction of 0%, 10%, and 30%.

[44,45], are desired to provide better insight in this question.

Conclusions

In this study, a combustion research unit equipped with a heavy-fuel oil injection system and a high-temperature chamber is used to investigate the spray combustion characteristics of FPBO and FPBO/ethanol blends. The pressure-based heat release analysis is used to evaluate fuel ignition and combustion characteristics, while a high-speed imaging

technique is adopted to visualize natural luminosity of spray flames. A wood based FPBO, and diesel, are first tested at a chamber wall temperature of 750 °C with an ambient pressure of 50 bar. Then the effects of injection pressure are studied. Finally, an investigation on the influence of ethanol addition (10% and 30%) is performed. The main findings from this study can be listed as follows.

- At injection pressures of 300 bar, the poor atomization of FPBO leads to so-called grainy spray flames, and nozzle orifices are quickly blocked within several injections. The increase of injection pressure to 900 bar could clearly improve the atomization quality, ignitability, and nozzle durability of FPBO.
- Compared with diesel, FPBO has a lower chemical reactivity while the peak heat release rate is comparable at the same conditions. FPBO has a lower sooting tendency, and it alleviates the end-of-injection dribble.
- Small amounts of ethanol addition could improve fuel atomization and further lower the sooting tendency even though the oxygen content of FPBO is higher than that of ethanol. A possible explanation is the different effectiveness in inhibiting soot formation between the oxygen-containing functional group and oxygen content coming from the fuel water content.
- Ethanol addition has a slight influence on FPBO ignition processes. The experimental results show that the ignition delay of FPBO is retarded by 10% ethanol addition, while it is advanced by 30% ethanol addition. This can be explained as the overall outcomes from the reduced physical ignition delay and a prolonged chemical ignition delay with the addition of ethanol.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yu Wang: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Noud Maes:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Michel Cuijpers:** Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Bart Somers:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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